

Domain wall dynamics in stress annealed microwires

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Abstract

In this work we investigate the effect of stress-annealing on the magnetic properties and domain wall dynamics of CoFeNi-based microwires with nearly-zero magnetostriction. Among the annealing parameters whose influence we studied are time and temperature, as well as the magnitude of the stresses applied during annealing. We demonstrate that heat treatment and stress application have the opposite effects on the switching field and domain wall mobility. Therefore, their combination can be used to tune the parameters of the domain wall dynamics over the wide range. We found that stress annealing can increase the domain wall mobility by up to 3 times comparing to annealing without any stress. The maximum domain wall mobility achieved for the studied microwire is 95 m²/sA.

Keywords: amorphous materials, ferromagnetic glass-coated microwires, domain wall dynamics, magnetostriction

Introduction

Amorphous ferromagnetic glass-coated wires are unique and one of the most widely researched composite objects. They offer a broad variety of physical phenomena and properties (magnetic bistability and extremely fast domain wall (DW) propagation, giant magneto-impedance effect, high magnetic permeability) that provide new application opportunities in sensors, logic, bioengineering, and magnetic tweezers [1-6].

Since the metal nucleus of microwires is amorphous, the micromagnetic structure and, consequently, the magnetic properties are determined by the shape anisotropy together with magnetoelastic anisotropy due to the interplay of the magnetostriction and presence of internal stresses [7]. The origin of these stresses is related to the fabrication method – rapid solidification of a metallic microwire surrounded by glass-coating from the melt (Taylor-Ulitovsky technique) [8]. The internal stresses magnitude evaluated for such fabrication method is in the range of 100 MPa-1 GPa [9]. The presence of internal mechanical stresses has

a significant effect on the magnetostriction coefficient and determines the magnitude of the magnetoelastic anisotropy in microwires [10-12].

Thus, microwires with positive magnetostriction coefficient (mainly Fe-based) can be considered as a single domain objects, where almost the entire volume of the microwire is occupied by an axially magnetized core, and a thin radial structure will exist on the periphery, occupying only a few % of the metallic nucleus volume. The axially magnetized core of a microwire consists of single large domain and closure domains at the ends of the microwire. In this case, the magnetization reversal along the microwire axis occurs with a large and single Barkhausen jump, i.e., the rapid propagation of a head-to-head or tail-to-tail domain wall along the microwire axis, resulting in magnetic bistability, which manifests itself in the form of a rectangular hysteresis loop [13]. The domain wall velocities reach several kilometers per second [13-19]. Microwires with negative magnetostriction coefficient (Co-based) have bamboo-like structure with magnetization reversal occurring by coherent rotation of magnetization vector, resulting in almost non-hysteretic magnetic behavior, and giant magneto-impedance (GMI) [20].

The values of switching field (a minimal field required to induce the DW motion in magnetically bistable microwires), DW velocity and GMI could vary depending on the chemical composition, microwire diameter, glass coating thickness and production parameters, which affect shape and magnetoelastic anisotropy. Therefore, the interplay between the components of the magnetoelastic anisotropy (namely, internal stress and magnetostriction coefficient), as well as the shape anisotropy, determine the magnetic properties of microwires with specific parameters. So, for example, submicron and nanometer amorphous microwires are bistable regardless of the composition of the metallic nucleus and the sign of the magnetostriction coefficient [21].

Another remarkable feature of amorphous microwires is the ability to change their magnetic properties as a result of post-processing, which can affect the magnetoelastic anisotropy. One of the most common ways to change the internal stress is thermal annealing. Since the internal stresses in amorphous microwires are a part of magnetoelastic energy and play an important role in micromagnetic structure formation, changing the value or distribution of stresses leads to the change of magnetic properties and micromagnetic structure [22-26]. Thus, in microwires with a nearly-zero negative magnetostriction coefficient, thermal annealing can cause a change in the sign of magnetostriction from negative to positive due to the internal stresses relaxation, which, in turn, will lead to a significant change in the micromagnetic structure and the magnetization reversal mechanism. Such microwires, where the magnetostriction coefficient became positive and in which magnetization reversal began to occur by the motion of the DW, will be referred to as microwires with induced (or acquired) bistability [13, 15-17].

The DW dynamics in microwires with acquired bistability can have its own peculiarities. This is due to the fact that on the periphery of such a microwire there is not a radial, but a circular domain structure, since a change in the sign of the magnetostriction coefficient leads to an increase in the axially magnetized core, but not to a reorientation of magnetic moments at the

periphery. Second, the magnitude of magnetostriction coefficient of such microwires is very small, which should contribute to a rather high mobility of the DW. In addition, the internal mechanical stresses reduced as a result of annealing also contribute to high mobility and velocity of the domain wall [13, 15-17].

Another efficient approach to vary the properties of microwires over a wider range is stress annealing. The

presence of external stresses during annealing can further modify the magnetoelastic anisotropy. Recently this post-processing method was applied to amorphous Fe- [13, 27] and Co-based [13, 28] and nanocrystalline Co-based [29] microwires. In this work we investigate the effect of stress-annealing on the magnetic properties and domain wall dynamics of CoFeNi-based microwires with nearly-zero magnetostriction.

Material and methods

For investigation we selected amorphous ferromagnetic glass-coated microwires produced by Taylor-Ulitovsky technique with a metal core composition of $\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Fe}_4\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$. Briefly, the Taylor-Ulitovsky technique of glass-coated microwires preparation involves melting of the metallic alloy using a high frequency inductor and consequent drawing of a metallic microwire inside the glass shell. Such glass-coated metallic microwire is then wound onto a rotating pick-up bobbin [8]. The diameter of the metallic core, d , was $17\ \mu\text{m}$ and the total diameter of the microwire in glass shell, D , was $23.6\ \mu\text{m}$. The length of studied microwire samples was 10 cm. The microwire samples were annealed for various times at temperatures, T_{ann} , of 200, 300, and 350 °C. The annealing time, t_{ann} , ranged from 1 to 60 minutes. The microwires were annealed in a conventional furnace both without applying any external stresses and under tensile axial stress of 125 and 250 MPa. For the stress-annealing, mechanical loads of different weights were attached to one of the microwire ends. After annealing, the magnetic properties of the microwire were studied, using an induction method and Vibrating Sample Magnetometer by LakeShore. The setup for the hysteresis loop tracking by induction method consists of a single-layered pick-up coil located inside a 15 cm long solenoid producing an axial homogeneous magnetic field. Studied 10 cm sample is placed inside the pick-up coil [27, 28]. In such setup the influence of the demagnetizing field and hence shape magnetic anisotropy contribution or microwires is negligible.

In case of induced during the annealing magnetic bistability, the velocity of the DW was measured as a dependence on the value of the external magnetic field. For investigation of the DW we used modified Sixtus-Tonks technique with 3 pick-up coils, which makes it possible to track the uniformity of the DW motion along the wire axis.

The difference of the employed setup with the classical Sixtus-Tonks experiments [30], is that we used three pick-up coils for correct determination of the DW velocity [7, 13-15]. In this setup, a microwire sample is placed inside a long and thin magnetization coil that creates a uniform magnetic field, H , and inside three pick-up coils, separated by the same distance and

also located inside the magnetization coil. One of the ends of the microwire is located outside the magnetizing coil, which makes it possible to activate the DW propagation from the opposite microwire end. The DW velocity, v , can be then evaluated as [7, 13]:

$$v = \frac{l}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

being l is the distance between pick-up coils and Δt is the time difference between the voltage peaks detected by the oscilloscope. We have paid attention only to the linear part of $v(H)$ dependencies, that corresponds to viscous DW propagation regime [7,13].

The magnetostriction coefficient of as-prepared and annealed samples was measured by the small angle magnetization rotation (SAMR) method [31]. Initially such method has been proposed for amorphous ribbons [31], however recently it was adapted for magnetic microwires [11, 32]. This method consists in saturating the sample with an axial magnetic field, while the transverse magnetic field created by AC current produces the small angle magnetization rotation [31, 32]. Upon applied tensile stress, σ , the magnetization rotation angle changes due to a change in the magnetic anisotropy field H_k . Accordingly, the magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , can be estimated from the $H_k(\sigma)$ dependence as:

$$\lambda_s = \frac{\mu_0 M_s dH_k}{3 d\sigma_k} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_0 M_s$ is the saturation magnetization.

Results and discussion

In as-prepared state the microwire had a negative magnetostriction coefficient $\lambda_s = -1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ and an S-shaped hysteresis loop. The magnitude of the magnetostriction coefficient is vanishing. In such amorphous alloys with vanishing λ_s , the stress dependence of λ_s can be relevant [33, 34]. Therefore, as recently shown experimentally [11], the relaxation of internal stress caused by annealing shifts the value of magnetostriction towards positive values and changes the sign of magnetostriction (it becomes positive after annealing). Thus, for the annealed microwire, we observe magnetic bistability. Figure 1a schematically illustrates the micromagnetic structure that corresponds to the magnetic properties of as-prepared and annealed microwire samples. Here, as an example, we used microwire annealed for 60 minutes at a temperature of 300 °C with external mechanical stress of $\sigma = 125$ MPa. The rectangular hysteresis loop for the annealed microwire indicates magnetization reversal by the fast DW propagation, which is typical for a micromagnetic structure in which the axial domain predominates in almost the entire volume of the microwire, while a thin layer with a circular structure remains at the periphery. So, we can deduce that due to the change of the magnetostriction coefficient induced by the stress relaxation the micromagnetic structure and, as a consequence, the mechanism of magnetisation reversal also changed.

Figure 1 a) Schematic illustration of the micromagnetic structure of $\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Fe}_4\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ microwires in a glass shell and corresponding hysteresis loops before annealing (as-prepared state, negative magnetostriction coefficient) and after annealing (positive magnetostriction coefficient); b) and c) Field dependences of the DW velocity, $v(H)$, and corresponding hysteresis loops of the $\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Fe}_4\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ microwire annealed under applied axial tensile stress, σ , of 0, 125 and 250 MPa for 5 and 60 minutes at a temperature, of 300°C (b) and 350°C (c). S is the DW mobility.

To evaluate the effect of external axial stresses during the annealing, the microwires were annealed both with applied tensile axial stresses of 125 and 250 MPa and without any stresses (0 MPa). The obtained hysteresis loops and field dependences of the DW velocity for all cases of stress application annealed at temperature 300 °C and 350 °C are shown in Figure 1b and 1c, respectively. A comparison of the hysteresis loops clearly shows that the application of tensile mechanical stresses directed along the microwire axis contributes to a decrease of the switching field that is the minimal value of the magnetic field required for DW nucleation and propagation. Axial tensile stresses, $\sigma = 250$ MPa applied during annealing reduce the switching field by about 4 times.

The DW dynamics in all studied samples can be described by linear $v(H)$ dependencies, as also reported for Fe- and Co-rich microwires [7,13]:

$$v = S(H - H_{sw}) \quad (3)$$

where S is the DW mobility and H_{sw} is the critical propagation field, below which the DW propagation cannot be observed.

The presence of external mechanical stresses can significantly change the value of the DW mobility: for a microwire annealed for 5 minutes at 300 °C, the DW mobility increased by ~ 3 times when a stress of 250 MPa was applied comparing to a microwire annealed under the same conditions, but without applying any stress. With an increase in the annealing temperature to 350 °C, the trend of changing the DW motion parameters remains the same as for a temperature of 300 °C. In addition, the effect of stress annealing is qualitatively similar regardless of the annealing time. Thus, evaluation of the effect of applied external mechanical stresses during annealing gives an unambiguous result and trend regardless of the annealing time (5-60 minutes) and temperature. However, it is worth mentioning that recently was reported that stress-annealing at high enough T_{ann} and σ leads to a loss of magnetic bistability induced by annealing [28].

The rate at which the relaxation processes of internal mechanical stresses proceed in the microwire, and, consequently, the change in magnetic anisotropy is directly proportional to the annealing temperature and time. Therefore, in order to clearly establish the trends in magnetic properties changes on the annealing time, the studied microwires were annealed at a temperature of 200 °C. The annealing time varied in the range from 1 to 60 minutes. Comparison of hysteresis loops at various annealing times and the dependence of the switching field on annealing time are shown in Figure 2a and 2b.

Figure 2. a-d) Results of $\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Fe}_4\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ microwire annealing at 200 °C with no external stress: a) hysteresis loops at various annealing time, t (1-60 minutes) and corresponding magnetic field dependencies of the DW velocity $v(H)$ c) the dependence of the switching field, H_{sw} on the annealing time, t (taken from the hysteresis loops). The red symbol marks the value of the coercive force of the microwire annealed for 1 minute d) dependence of the DW mobility, S , on the annealing time, t . e) and f) Hysteresis loops and field dependencies of the DW velocity, $v(H)$, of the

microwire annealed at a temperature of 350°C for 5 and 60 minutes with applied stresses of 125 MPa (e) and 250 MPa (f)

Magnetization reversal of the microwire annealed for 1 minute occurs combining two processes – a jump corresponding to the fast DW propagation along the microwire axis and gradual change of the magnetization related to the coherent rotation of the magnetic moment. It implies that there are two comparable regions in the metallic nucleus having two magnetization reversal mechanisms: axially magnetized core in the center and circular magnetic structure at the periphery. However, it was not possible to measure the field dependence of the DW velocity in the microwire sample annealed for 1 minute due to the absence of a signal. Increasing annealing time to two minutes leads to magnetic bistability manifested in the rectangular hysteresis loop and demonstrates predominance of the axially magnetized region in the metallic nucleus. Longer annealing results in increasing switching fields (Figure 2d), which is presumably caused by an increase in the absolute value of the magnetostriction coefficient. The results of the annealing influence on magnetostriction coefficient value and sign of CoFeNi-based amorphous ferromagnetic microwires are provided in Refs [11] and [34]. The change in the λ_s affects the magnetoelastic anisotropy, which is one of the most important contributions to the overall magnetic anisotropy in amorphous ferromagnetic objects and the formation of the micromagnetic structure.

Figure 2b presents the field dependence of the DW velocity for microwires annealed for 2-60 minutes. Longer annealing times lead to pronounced enhancement of the switching field, which correlates with the tendency observed from the hysteresis loops. This also entails the increase in the DW velocity with annealing time: from 710 m/s for 2 minutes annealing to 1724 m/s for 30 minutes annealing. However, the DW mobility, S , of the DW drops by three times (Figure 2c), which reveals the magnetoelastic anisotropy change that can be caused by the λ_s increase. This assumption is supported by the results presented in [11] obtained for the FeCoNi-based microwire with similar chemical composition. The authors demonstrated that at annealing temperature up to 320 °C the increase of the annealing time from 1 to 128 minutes leads to the magnetostriction coefficient increase. For microwires stress-annealed at higher temperature (300 °C and 350 °C) we observe the same tendency in switching field changes (Figure 2e and f).

Microwires with magnetic bistability acquired as a result of annealing have a number of peculiarity, such as the presence of a circular domain structure at the periphery, small switching fields, and very high values of DW mobility, which makes studying the dynamics of DW motion in the presence of external mechanical stresses topical. To study the dynamics of DW motion in the presence of external mechanical stresses, tensile stresses in the range from 5 to 45 MPa were applied to microwires with acquired magnetic bistability during the measurement of the field dependence of the DW velocity.

Figure 3. Field dependencies of the DW velocity, $v(H)$, at various values of axial mechanical stress applied during the measurement to the microwire a) annealed at 350 °C under applied mechanical stress of 125 MPa for 60 minutes, b) annealed at 350 °C under applied mechanical stress of 250 MPa for 5 minutes.

The results show that the annealing temperature has a significant effect on the DW dynamics under applied stress. At an $T_{ann} = 300$ °C the observed trends in the change in the dynamics of the DW propagation was the same as for the microwires with spontaneous bistability: the velocity of the DW movement decreases. However, an increase in the annealing temperature up to 350 °C leads to the opposite results. Figure 3 shows two plots of the field dependencies of the DW velocity at different values of mechanical stresses applied during the measurement to microwires annealed at 350 °C. One can see that $v(H)$ curves are located one above the other for different values applied during the measurement of stresses, moreover, the curves corresponding to the greater value of mechanical stresses are located above. This indicates an increase in the DW velocity with an increase in the applied stresses. Similar results (increase in DW velocity upon applied stress) was previously also reported for other Co-rich microwire with induced by annealing magnetic bistability [35]. It can also be noted that the range of magnetic field values, in which the magnetization reversal of the microwire is realized by moving one DW, decreases with an increase in external loads.

Thus, annealing of CoFeNi-based microwires with nearly-zero negative magnetostriction leads to a shift of the magnetostriction coefficient toward positive values and a change of sign from negative to positive at a certain annealing duration, as a result of which the microwire becomes magnetically bistable. Analyzing the results obtained and taking into account [11, 23], we can conclude that an increase in the annealing time (we consider the case where the annealing time is longer than that necessary for the formation of magnetic bistability) leads to an increase in the absolute value of the magnetostriction coefficient due to internal stress relaxation. As a result, we observe an increase in the switching field (which is directly proportional to the magnetostriction value [35]) and a decrease in DW mobility (which is inversely proportional to the magnetostriction value [36]). When axial stresses are applied during annealing, the reverse effect is observed: a decrease in the switching field and an increase in DW mobility. This trend can be explained by the fact that the application of stresses reduces the absolute value of the magnetostriction, which was demonstrated in [33, 34] for both microwires with

positive and negative magnetostriction coefficients. Opposite effects from annealing and stress application allow not only to obtain microwires with acquired bistability, but also change the characteristics of the DW dynamics over a wide range. It is important to note that the microwire with acquired bistability has very high values of the DW mobility reaching $95 \text{ m}^2/\text{sA}$, which is up to 5 times higher than for an initially bistable microwire [25, 27].

Conclusion

Thus, we have comprehensively analyzed the effect of annealing parameters with applied stresses on the DW dynamics in the $\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Fe}_4\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ microwire with acquired bistability. We have been able to separate the contributions of heat treatment and stress application and have shown that they have the opposite effects. Conventional annealing leads to an increase in the switching field and a decrease in DW mobility due to growth of the magnetostriction coefficient. The presence of external stress when annealing interferes with the process of relaxation of internal stresses and growth of the magnetostriction coefficient, thus causing significant switching field reduction and very high DW mobility of stress annealed microwires. Stress annealing can reduce the switching field by 4 times and increase the DW mobility up to 3 times compared to microwire annealed without any stress.

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